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PEDAGOGICAL WAYS OF FORMING SENIOR PRESCHOOLER'S LINGUISTIC ABILITIES

Abstract: *The article discusses the importance of forming senior preschooler's linguistic abilities at the same time revealing children's speech difficulties. As the solution of the problem pedagogical ways are proposed aimed to the formation of senior preschooler's linguistic abilities providing children's self-manifestation and free self-expression. The proposed pedagogical ways are derived from children's internal opportunities of perceiving language.*

Key words: *linguistic ability, pedagogical approaches, senior preschooler, language unit, speech difficulties.*

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Педагогічні шляхи формування мовних здібностей у старшого дошкільника

У статті обговорюється важливість формування мовних здібностей старшого дошкільника з одночасним виявленням мовленнєвих труднощів. Для розв'язання проблеми пропонуються педагогічні шляхи, які спрямовані на формування мовних здібностей старшого дошкільника та забезпечують вільне самовираження дітей. Запропоновані педагогічні шляхи засновані на внутрішніх можливостях дітей сприймати мову.

The effectiveness of the various educational activities in preschool educational institutions is conditioned with children's verbal and communicative abilities, which should not only ensure the final results of the curriculum, but also the continuity of education.

Despite the fact that there are a number of studies on preschooler's speech development, nevertheless, today inadequate level of preschoolers' speech literacy is considered, which is, particularly, connected with the fact that the process of speech development is realizing on pre-designed rules, often incomprehensible to children, molding the child's ability to master the mother tongue, which doesn't support the child in matters of self-organization and free expression.

Observing the process of mastering language units by the children, we can say that the development of his/her language abilities occurs in the case of ensuring the diversity of oral speech, different types of activities, communication forms. On the one hand, verbal activity, mediated by the language system and conditioned with the situation, stimulates the formation of

new forms of communication, on the other hand, the latter promote the organization and expansion of verbal activity [1, p. 24]. It means that a possible motivation for the development of a preschooler's oral speech is the desire to express his/ her own thoughts, preferences, interests, self-expression, which is manifested in communicative, verbal situations. In this case, the internal mechanisms of organizing speech are activated, motivating the child to choose appropriate units of language, interconnect them, plan, choose the sequence of speech, control the language material internally and manifest freely. At the same time, during speech activity, the child listens, perceives the others' speech, evaluates not only own, but others' speech as well [2, p. 92].

This means that the criterion for a preschooler's developed speech should be considered internally (internal speech organization) and externally (external & self-assessment of speech) controlled speech, which is the result of developed linguistic abilities. Consequently, preschooler's oral literate speech, conditioned with linguistic abilities, is formed and developed during the activities organized with children, different types of work, communication, organization of different verbal situations.

Considering the process of developing senior preschooler's linguistic abilities, it should be noted that at this age child's pronunciation is becoming clearer and more definite. Senior preschooler is able to easily determine the direction of the voice, distinguish his/her friends voices, control the power of his own voice, use the means of expression, clearly uttering interrogative, exclamatory sentences. At this age, the child performs a phonetic analysis of the word, distinguishing both the first and last sounds of the given word, as well as in the word. At this stage, a dichotomy of conjugation isn't noticed, the child uses the singular-plural forms of the noun correctly, the tenses of the verb. 5-6 aged child shows interest in the meaning of the word, uses synonyms, antonyms, different parts of speech [4, p. 87].

The development of a senior preschooler's speech is more related to the perception of the meaning of word, when at this age the word, detaching from the material meaning, goes beyond the child's sensory experience and gets cognitive meaning. From this point of view, senior preschooler's speech acquires a new quality. Hence, the child does not master the mother tongue mechanically, but is oriented in the units of language, on the basis of which he/she formulates his/her own thoughts and expresses coherent speech.

Though the above-mentioned speech peculiarities during our study with senior preschoolers we have found out the following linguistic difficulties: 1) incorrect pronunciation of separate sounds, 2) determination of place of sound in the word, 3) improper use of expression means, 4) choice of synonyms and antonyms, 5) choice of appropriate words in separate situations, 6) incorrect expression of singular and plural forms of the noun, 7) inappropriate expression of thought through insufficient means of communication, 8) disorder of the sequence of sentences, events, constraint of speech, 9) difficulties in perceiving speech.

It is obvious that child's abilities of own speech organization and expression are constrained.

The mentioned difficulties, however, are also transferred to primary school, causing a low level of children's progress [3, p. 8].

Hence, the formation and development of children's linguistic abilities should become a priority of the educational process in preschool institutions, ensuring the effectiveness of children's further activities.

In our work aimed at developing senior preschoolers' linguistic abilities among thirty children of the experimental group, we provided children's self-organization and control of speech by choosing the appropriate language units and free expression of speech. For that purpose, we based on the following pedagogical approaches proposed by us:

- ✓ providing motivations for speech expression, cognitive interests, promoting children's speech activity,
- ✓ organization of children's speech activity promoting free speech,
- ✓ providing children's free and self-expression (creating communicative, different speech situations and discussion), preventing the mechanical reproduction of speech by the children.

The work carried out by us with the experimental group promoted children to organize and express their own speech and manifest themselves freely. This helped them to participate in the discussions, conversations, perceive the meaning of others' speech, give complete answers to the questions.

The children initiated conversations with peers, expressed their own ideas about familiar phenomena, described them, tried to find out about unfamiliar objects to them by asking questions using the words "When", "Why", "How", expressed their thoughts freely. They tested their own thoughts by choosing the necessary linguistic units, comparing and contrasting them with each other. This contributed to the effective perception of the mother tongue by organizing own thoughts to self-organization and free expression.

In order to reveal the effectiveness of our work with the children of the experimental group, we analyzed the obtained data, which we have presented in the form of a diagram /Diagram 1/. We compared the initial and final results of the development of children's linguistic abilities in experimental group:

Diagram 1. Comparative analysis of the experimental group

We obtained the presented data by four diagnostic methodologies ("Name words" by R. S. Nemov, "Telling", "Name it in a word" by V. N. Makarova, E. A. Stavtseva, M. N. Edakova, and the diagnostic methodology by O. S. Ushakova). The gained results by the mentioned methodologies were generalized.

According to the results, among 30 children the high level is 57%, which means that 17 children have a high level of developed linguistic abilities, the average level is 32% (10 children) and the low level is 11% (3 children), while according to the initial results of the same group, the high level was 16% (4 children), the average level 32% (10 children), the low level 52% (16 children).

Thus, basing on the theoretically and experimentally reliable data of the problem, we can say that in the developing process of senior preschoolers' linguistic abilities such pedagogical-methodological approaches, means and forms are important, which do not lead to mechanical reproduction of children's speech, but deriving from the children's opportunity of perceiving the mother tongue, provide their free speech, self-expression, initiation to communicate, contributing to the development of the linguistic abilities.

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